

Research

Climatic Variability and Wetland Resources in Rupa Lake Catchment, Nepal

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Abstract Climatic variability with temperature increase is serious concern for wetland resource management and regulates the benefits. Key informant interview (n=5), focus group discussion (n=4) and household survey (n=60) were undertaken to appraise the local experience regarding status of wetland resources with climatic variability. Local households were stratified and chosen close settlement as respondents for the study. Meteorological data from 1979 to 2009 were used to analyze climatic trends where least-squares curve fitting technique was used to appraise trend. We observed both maximum mean temperature and minimum mean temperature have been annually increasing with the rate of 0.049°C and 0.040°C respectively, where overall temperature was found to be increased at the rate of 0.045°C annually. The mean maximum temperature was recorded ever the highest 28°C in 2009, and seasonal maximum and minimum temperature trend of the winter was higher (0.051 and 0.067), which can be perceived as indication of global warming. The annual precipitation trend was increasing but Monsoon and winter precipitation was found to be decreasing, which directly affects wetland resource and agricultural productivity. Promotion of indigenous knowledge with training and education are suggested as the best option for coping the problems.

Keywords: Local, Global warming, Meteorological Data, Eutrophication, Cope

Introduction

Climate change is one of the most serious threats to natural resources and livelihoods (IPCC, 2007). The projected change in temperature above the baseline average is 1.2 °C for 2030 and 1.7°C for 2050 and 3.0°C for 2100 (OECD, 2003). Nepal as a part of the earth cannot remain untouched to Global climate change. Although, Nepal is responsible for only about 0.0255 of the total annual greenhouse gas emission of the world (Karki, 2007). It is experiencing increasing trends and the associated effects of global warming. It already observed such as an increase in the dry period, intense rainfall, food, landside, forest fire, glacial threats and GLOF threats (Shreth, 2007). In Nepal, the mean temperature is steadily increasing at the rate of 0.04°C year⁻¹. This mean temperature has increased by 1.7 °C between 1975 and 2005. The regional mean annual temperature trend is more at higher altitudes than in the lower one.

The mean annual temperature, in general, is in a rising trend in almost the entire country except for a slightly decreasing trend in isolated patches. Monsoon rainfall occurring during the June-September period constitutes more than 80% of the total rainfall in Nepal which varies from about 150 mm to over 5000mm per annum. Developing countries are more vulnerable to the effects of climate change due to its high dependence on climate-sensitive sectors like glaciers, agriculture and forestry, and its low financial adaptive capacity (Karki, 2007).

Wetlands are among the world's most productive and diverse ecosystems and have social, economic, religious, recreational, spiritual, cultural and historical significances (RCS, 2006). Freshwater wetlands cover 1% of Earth's surface hold more than 40% of the earth's species and 12% of all animal species (Schuyt, 2004). Nepal's wetland covers 5% area of the country and supports the traditional livelihood of over 11% population of the country (IUCN, Nepal, 2004). Continuously rising temperature has been drying wetlands which is becoming major concern of Nepal as well. So, there is an urgent need to understand the situation socially and biologically. The importance of wetlands in addition with climatic variability and suggest mitigation and adaptation measure to cope the situation. This study attempted to explore local experience about tendency of wetland resources with respect to climate change.

Materials and Methods

Study area

Lekhnath “City of seven lakes” is located in the southeast of Pokhara valley, Nepal. Out of 7 lakes having international importance, Rupa Lake is one of them and situated nearby Begnas Lake separated with small hillock Pacha Bhaiya forest. Rupa Lake occupied 115 hectares whose average depth is 6m (Oli, 2000). This North-east and southwest side of this Eutrophic Lake is covered with marshes and indigenous paddies. Local people are undertaking various activities and developing it as source of monetary income (Tamrakar, 2008). The reasons behind choosing Rupa Lake as study site are; local livelihood dependency on wetland resources, wetland of international importance, observation of preliminary impacts of e of climate variability, vulnerability of local livelihood and availability of meteorological data.

Fig.1. Map of the Rupa Lake, Kaski District, Nepal (Source: LiBIRD)

Data collection and analysis

We stratified wetland dependent communities in 2 groups as closer (households situated within the range of 200m from the lake boundary) and distant (farther than 200 meters from) dependent groups. We targeted closer groups for study because this community comparatively more depend on wetland resources and vulnerable from climate change perspective. Among selected group, we randomly chose 60 households (24% of total household of closer group) and entertained questionnaire survey (60 households), organized focus group discussion (4 groups) and interviewed key informants interview (5 persons) to collect the data.

In addition, the Transect walk was done with the help of local people to appraise and observe consequences of climatic variability and locally embraced adaptation measures. We followed transect walk as per Mascarenhas (1990) walking with or by local people through an area, observing, asking, listening, discussing, identifying local induced technology, etc. seeking problems, solutions and opportunities. Meteorological data of 30 years (from 1983 to 2009) were collected from the nearest meteorological station (about 15 kilometer far from the study site) of Pokhara, Nepal.

Data analysis

The least-squares curve fitting technique was used to find a linear trend in the data. The linear trend between the time series data (y) and time (t) is given in the equation ($y = a + bt$), where y = temperature or precipitation, time (t) years and “a” and “b” are the constants estimated by the principle of least squares. Similarly, analysis tools; SPSS 11.5, MS excel 2008 were used to analyze data and present in graphs and tables.

Result and discussion

Consequences of climatic variability: Based on the questionnaire interview, key informant survey, focus group discussion and transect walk with field observation, following major consequences of climate change were recorded (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Local indicators of climate change

Climatic Variability

Temperature: We found that the mean annual temperature is increasing at the rate of $0.045^{\circ}\text{C year}^{-1}$. Similarly, maximum mean temperature and minimum mean temperature are annually increasing at the rate of 0.049°C and $0.040^{\circ}\text{C year}^{-1}$ respectively. The seasonal minimum temperature trend (SMinTT) and seasonal maximum temperature trend (SMaxTT) of all the seasons in degree Celsius are also had increasing trends (Table 1). According to the SAGUN (2009), Nepal's temperature is rising by about 0.14°C .

Table 1. SMinTT, SMaxTT and SMPTT

Seasons	SMinTT	SMaxTT	SMPTT
Winter	0.051	0.067	-0.439
Pre-Monsoon	0.040	0.046	1.747
Monsoon	0.024	0.044	-0.172
Post monsoon	0.058	0.034	1.173

Precipitation: The average annual rainfall recorded in Pokhara city is 3,755mm (Regmi et al., 2007). The data shows that there was great fluctuation in the average rainfall showing erratic behavior in yearly precipitation but the rainfall trend is increasing by 0.464 per annum. The seasonal mean precipitation trend (SMPTT) shows that the winter and Monsoons are decreasing at the rate of -0.439 and -0.172 per year respectively (Table 1). 90% of farmers depend on winter and Monsoon rain for their agriculture cultivation. On the other hand, Pre-monsoon and Post monsoon precipitation was increasing at the rate of 1.747 and 1.173 respectively. Nepal receives the highest monthly rainfall in July and lowest in November. The annual precipitation pattern is dominated by Monsoon (Practical action, 2009). Our analysis shows that 79.6% annual precipitation occurs in Monsoon season whereas 4.2 %, 3.5%, and 12.7% occur during post-monsoon, winter and pre-monsoon respectively (Table 1). Monsoon rainfall constitutes more than 80% of the total rainfall in Nepal (Gauchan, 2010).

Drought trend: By combining the monthly values of precipitation expressed in millimeters (P) and temperature in centigrade degrees (T), biologically dry month is defined by ratio $P < 2T$ (Bagnouls and Gaussen, 2010). Analysis 30 years monthly data of precipitation and temperature shows that January, November, and December were found to dry months since these months temperature when assumed double the value exceeds the total precipitation received on these months (Table 2). Out of these three months, November is the driest month (Table 2).

Table: 2. Monthly mean precipitation (MP) and mean temperature (MT) of 30 years

	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	Jul.	Aug.	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec.
MP	22.8	34.5	59.9	126.6	364.0	675.4	938.4	848.4	645.0	140.5	17.4	21.6
MT	13.3	15.6	19.5	22.7	24.2	25.7	25.9	26.0	25.0	22.0	17.9	14.5

Consequence of climatic variability in on wetland resources

Nepal is rich in biodiversity and regarded as hotspot for some locally and globally significant plants and animals. Biodiversity hotspots are vulnerable to climate change because they are rich in endemic species (ICIMOD, 2009). More than 60% of respondents said biodiversity is getting decline with compare to past because of climatic variability and its effects. We found that people were experiencing negative consequences of climatic variability in biodiversity.

Fish diversity: Fish is one of the major sources of income of the local people residing around the wetlands. A total of 186 species of fishes are available in Nepal, in which 25 species were recorded in Rupa Lake (Oli, 1996) and 13 are native (IUCN, 1999). CBR (2008) recorded 32 fish species in the Lake where 21 are indigenous and 11 are introduced. According to local, native fishes like *Acrossocheilus hexagonolepsis*, *Anguilla spp.*, *Puntius ticto*, *Puntitus sarana* have been declining tremendously. About 90% respondents agreed that native fishes are declining due to water pollution, eutrophication, habitat shrinkage, illegal collection and introduction of exotic fish species. Out of which, 70% are strongly agreed that native fishes are decreasing due to unfavorable weather condition though the lake management activities were being organized regularly.

Herpetofauna diversity: Over 10,300 species of herpetofauna are found in the world whereas 190 species are recorded in Nepal including 64 globally threatened or IUCN red-listed. 14 species are endemic to Nepal. According to Baral 2008, 36 species of herpetofauna are recorded in Rupa and Begnas lake area comprising 12 amphibians, 9 lizards, 1 turtle, and 13 snakes. Of these, *Melanochelys tricarinata*, *Xenochropis santijohannis* and *Limnonectes nepalensis* were first time recoded Baral (2008). Out of 60 respondents, 70% believe that herpetofauna are also declining very rapidly with the change in temperature.

Waterfowls diversity: The avifauna of Nepal includes a total of 900 species of which 2 are endemic. Over 193 species of water fowls are recorded in Nepal (Kafle et al., 2008). Kafle (2011) recorded 36 waterfowls in Rupa Lake area. *Aythya nyroca*, *Motacilla citreola* and *Ana acuta* are vulnerable waterfowls recorded in our study site. 80% respondents believed that reduction of water floating grass, nesting pockets of birds are now no more available due to water pollution and sedimentation, as well as the introduction of exotic fish species like Grass carp.

Aquatic animals and plant diversity: 34 mammals, including aquatic mammals called Otter, were found in Rupa Lake (Regmi et al., 2007). Five species of Otter are found in Asia out of them *Lutra lutra*, *Lutra perspicillata*, *Aonyx cinerea* are found in Nepal. Both *Lutra lutra* and *Lutra perspicillata* were recorded Rupa Lake (Regmi et al., 2007) People reported that aquatic otter in Rupa Lake was frequent in the last decades but now they are not seen. The main reason

behind its decline was habitat destruction. 70% respondent said that shrinkage and siltation of lake is the major reason behind it. Similarly, *Trapanatus spp* which has major food value is decreasing day by day. Its root is used to cure Jaundice. Lotus species like *Nelumbium nuciferum* and *Nymphaea alba* are used for religious purposes and bathing with water of water lotus cure many skin diseases. Many native plants are decreasing due to climatic induced effects and human interventions. 75% of respondents believed that these native and valuable plants are declined due to the introduction of grass crab but 25% believed that it's not only grass crab it all because of water pollution and spread of invasive species.

Invasion form introduced species: New plants and animals species introduced in an area are considered as alien, exotic or non- native (Tiwari et al., 2005). About 8,000 plant species either traded or non-traded are expected to be agricultural weeds out of which 2500 species are taken as harmful. In Nepal, *Lantana camera* and *Chromolaena*, *Mikania micrantha* are alien invasive (Tiwari et al., 2000). Wetlands of Nepal are facing the problem of increasing unwanted plants. World's worst invasive alien plants species are *Caulerpa taxifolia*, *Spartina anglica*, *Undaria pinnatifida*, *Eichhornia crassipes*. Water hyacinth is the major threats to wetlands and Rupa Lake is also not free from invasion. Although there are few studies on the spread of invasive species, local communities have already experienced the emergence of species they have never seen in their lives (SAGUN, 2009). 70% of respondents said that invasive species are increasing due to global warming and water pollution which are creating the favorable condition to nonnative species.

Impact on local people: Decreases in the productivity of rice of the local dwellers due to scarcity of irrigation from the lake. The productivity of *Zea mays*, *Solanum tubersum*, *Triticum aestivum* was also decreasing and created extra financial burdens for survival. Agricultural pests and diseases are increasing, pest and pathogen effects were found to be common. 70% of respondents believed a rise in temperature and water pollution results in mosquito problems and parasitic diseases. Spread of diseases like Malaria and dengue are also major threats. Communities have experienced intense heat for the last ten years that resulted in the development of allergies and itching problems (SAGUN, 2009).

Conclusion

Climate change is not only international but also local concern which has resulted negative consequences in wetland dependent group and resources. The maximum mean temperature and minimum mean temperature of lake area having international importance is annually increasing at the rate of 0.049⁰C and 0.040⁰C respectively. Monsoon and winter precipitation are decreasing however the precipitation trend is increasing which directly affects productivity because our agriculture practice is highly based on traditional calendars. Similarly, Local dwellers have experienced unusual changes in temperature and rainfall patterns, which are supported by a number of indicators such as intense rainfall, unseasonal rainfall, loss of biodiversity, low agriculture productivity, invasion of weeds, an outbreak of pests and diseases, change in the agricultural calendar. Impacts are unlimited but coping mechanism is limited. Therefore, local adaptation-based wetland resource management practices through training and education are recommended to minimize the vulnerability and sustainable utilization of wetland resources.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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